

Using Hybrid Chatbot-Expert Panels and a Novel Fuzzy Group BWM to Build Consensus on Scientific Concepts

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Abstract

This paper proposes a methodology for reconciling expert assessments under uncertainty to arrive at a consensual definition of a scientific concept. The procedure combines human and large language model-assisted aggregation and summarization of expert proposals with fuzzy cluster analysis and a novel fuzzy group Best-Worst Method. The concept of traps in resilience science is used as an example. Two human jurors and two chatbots (ChatGPT and Gemini) clustered 30 expert proposals by content similarity. Due to low inter-juror agreement, another round was necessary to establish overarching themes, which were then incorporated into four proposals. These themes, along with the definition structure, were used in expert evaluation using fuzzy Best-Worst Method with an improved weight derivation model. In the fuzzy linear programming model, the possibility level (α) is introduced, which influences the tightness of constraints and improves consistency. The final consensual definition was determined using the novel Similarity-Awarded fuzzy group Best-Worst Method (SAfBWM), which assigns greater weight to alternatives that receive more consensual ratings and adjusts weights when two alternatives are rated equally. The smaller differences between individual and group weights produced by SAfBWM, compared to those generated by arithmetic mean aggregation, suggest that SAfBWM facilitates greater consensus. With weights of 0.38 and 0.34, ChatGPT and Gemini led the rankings, while the human jurors' definitions lagged behind at 0.16 and 0.12. These results highlight the potential of combining uncertain human judgment with AI and fuzzy MCDA in expert panels seeking consensus.

Keywords Best-Worst Method; Clustering; Large language models; Multi-criteria decision-making; Fuzzy linear programming

37 **1 Introduction**

38 **1.1 A Framework for Developing Concepts Through Consensus**

39 The conceptualization of terms forms the bedrock upon which scientific research and theory-building rest.
40 Clear and precise definitions provide a framework for empirical investigation, the accumulation of knowledge,
41 and the advancement of theory (Caws, 1959; Kuhn, 2012). However, aligning and standardizing terminology
42 across disciplines and perspectives remains a challenge, because different disciplines often operate with
43 distinct epistemological assumptions and contextual priorities.

44 To reconcile conflicting viewpoints, experts should engage in an extensive iterative dialogue, both within and
45 across disciplines (Huutoniemi et al., 2010; Vantard et al., 2023). Through the exchange of ideas, key terms
46 and principles are gradually defined and may serve as the building blocks for formal consensus (Baaden et al.,
47 2024). Because experts usually scrutinize proposed definitions through the lens of their own disciplines, group-
48 based process plays a critical role in refining initial proposals, ensuring they withstand academic scrutiny and
49 contribute meaningfully to the advancement of knowledge (Laudel, 2006). A group of jurors is typically needed
50 to guide the group process, identify key themes in the proposed definitions, and explore the existence of
51 consensus among experts (Carlile and Christensen, 2005; Khodyakov et al., 2023).

52 **1.2 Large Language Models (LLMs) in Content Analysis**

53 Manual content analysis by jurors is often demanding, time-consuming and prone to bias. Jurors may,
54 consciously or unconsciously, favor certain topics due to professional background, psychological preferences,
55 risk attitudes or their mental models (Xu et al., 2023; Schuerkamp et al., 2025), and may assign these topics as
56 initial means in a mental quasi k-means clustering of proposals. Machine clustering of proposed definitions
57 using large language models (LLMs) offers promising support in distilling perspectives from diverse domains
58 (Gimpel et al., 2023; 2024). LLMs can automatically group similar definitions into clusters, facilitating
59 comparative analysis and synthesis (Glickman and Zhang, 2024). Using text summarizers, generative LLMs
60 can also efficiently distill a multitude of proposed definitions into a concise summary (Saleh et al., 2024). This
61 process aids in reconciling discrepancies among proposed definitions and saves time. Beyond the analytical
62 phase, generative LLMs can also be employed in the synthetic phase by formulating new definitions based on
63 key themes and terms identified and agreed upon by experts. The proposals generated by LLMs can be fine-
64 tuned, allowing for faster convergence towards consensus among contributors. Despite the considerable
65 potential of LLMs in terminology, a methodological framework for LLM-assisted consensual decision-making
66 in concept definition has not been presented. In this study, we present a consensus-stimulating group multi-
67 criteria decision-making (MCDM) method designed for such use cases.

68 **1.3 Fuzzy Consensual Multi-Criteria Evaluation**

69 Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods provide a structured approach to evaluating alternatives
70 against multiple criteria, ensuring transparency and incorporating expert perspectives (Sahoo and Goswami,
71 2023; Chen et al., 2024). In terminology, the criteria for evaluating a term are substantive and structure-related.
72 Substantive criteria depend on the subject and its complexity and should be determined through group
73 discussion. Structure-related criteria, on the other hand, evaluate the structure of the definition, its clarity and
74 sufficiency to describe the concept. Scientific definitions should be evaluated with respect to several
75 *differentiae*, i.e., the distinguishing characteristics of the term (see Supplementary Information).

76 There are numerous MCDM methods, each based on different methodological frameworks. These include the
77 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the Best-Worst Method (BWM), the Technique for Order of Preference
78 by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), the Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment
79 Evaluations (PROMETHEE) and Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT), among others. A comprehensive
80 literature review shows that BWM (Rezaei, 2015), a flexible and intuitive method based on pairwise
81 comparisons, has several advantages over other MCDM methods (Ecer, 2024). It is easy to implement,
82 supports hierarchical structures and accommodates group expert input. It allows experts to focus on the best
83 and worst criteria, helping to avoid unnecessary complexity and reduce bias (Dehshiri et al., 2022). BWM also
84 offers benefits in terms of consistency and reliability, as the number of pairwise comparisons increases linearly
85 with the number of elements, compared to a quadratic increase in AHP, resulting in a higher degree of
86 reliability due to the higher consistency of pairwise comparisons (Ahmad et al., 2017). Recently, several
87 methods have been proposed to derive priority weights in BWM, including for group decision-making
88 problems (Xu and Wang, 2024); however, the question of how to handle uncertainty and imprecision remains
89 open.

90
91 In certain cases, experts may not be able to express their preferences precisely because the concept is vague or
92 lacks the *differentia*. In such cases, linguistic evaluations and the concept of fuzzy logic can be applied (Zadeh,
93 1965). Using fuzzy logic, experts can express their preferences using linguistic terms, which are then
94 transformed into fuzzy numbers to handle uncertainty and imprecision. Recent studies highlight the growing
95 use of hybrid MCDM approaches that integrate fuzzy logic to enhance decision accuracy and robustness
96 (Kumar, 2025). However, the challenge lies in incorporating the inherent uncertainties that characterize
97 individual judgments into a group decision. Traditional MCDM methods may not adequately capture these
98 nuances. To address this issue, advanced fuzzy group MCDM methods are needed to ensure that the final group
99 ranking truly reflects the uncertain nature of expert preferences (Shahmohammad et al., 2024). One such
100 method is fuzzy BWM (Guo and Zhao, 2017), which has recently been applied in many fields, including
101 sustainability (Foroozesh et al., 2022; Parsa Rad et al., 2024), the environment (Banihashemi and Khalilzadeh,
102 2023; Majumder et al., 2023), healthcare (Gao et al., 2024; KhanMohammadi et al., 2023), and the Internet of
103 Things (Ogundoyin and Kamil, 2023). To derive weights using fuzzy BWM, Hafezalkotob and Hafezalkotob

104 (2017) presented a model in the form of a linear program based on fuzzy constraints, which are then converted
105 into very loose ordinary constraints. This model has been used in aviation (Gao et al., 2023) and product design
106 applications (Maghsoodi et al., 2019). However, it encounters challenges in measuring inconsistency. It tends
107 to show very low inconsistency even in situations with highly inconsistent pairwise comparisons. In this study,
108 we propose an adaptation of the fuzzy BWM developed by Hafezalkotob and Hafezalkotob (2017) to address
109 its shortcomings.

110 The aggregation of expert opinions into group evaluations is the most challenging component of group
111 decision-making (Mohammadi et al., 2023). The most commonly used operators for aggregation are the
112 arithmetic mean, geometric mean, power mean, minimum and maximum, or ordered average (Li et al., 2024b).
113 However, these operators are not suitable for aggregating pairwise comparisons in BWM, where experts select
114 different best and worst elements. They are more appropriate for aggregating individual weights. To optimize
115 group performance, a certain level of consensus should be reached, not too low, but also not extremely high
116 (Massari et al., 2019). Aggregation methods that consider the agreement or similarity between expert
117 judgments can lead to an acceptable consensus group decision (Guo and Qi, 2021). To achieve a consensual
118 final decision, the process of aggregating individual weights into group weights using weighted arithmetic
119 mean should reward the consensual behavior of the experts. Therefore, we have integrated the Similarity-
120 Awarded Group Method (Šmidovnik and Grošelj, 2023) into a novel fuzzy BWM called Similarity-Awarded
121 fuzzy group BWM (SAfBWM). SAfBWM considers the best elements of all experts; if several experts choose
122 the same best element, their weights and consequently the weight of that element are increased.

123 The aim of this paper is therefore to showcase a methodological framework for consensual group decision-
124 making that integrates LLM-based chatbots with expert evaluations and a novel consensus-stimulating fuzzy
125 group multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA). The proposed framework can be applied to any scientific
126 domain that requires consensual group decisions. In this paper we demonstrate it on the study of a consensual
127 definition of the concept of traps in rural mountain areas. In the next chapter (chapter 1.4) we briefly introduce
128 traps as a multifaceted concept in social-ecological research.

129 **1.4 Traps: A Multifaceted Concept in Social-Ecological Research**

130 Traps in the broadest sense are scenarios in which individuals or entire societies embark on certain resilient
131 directions or relationships that later prove unpleasant or even detrimental, with no apparent means of retreat
132 or avoidance (Platt, 1973). Gunderson and Holling (2002) were the first to identify the possible negative
133 consequences of resilience for development, introducing the concept of social-ecological traps. Social-
134 ecological traps describe situations where self-reinforcing social and ecological feedback loops maintain or
135 push a social-ecological system towards an undesirable state that may be difficult or impossible to reverse
136 (Cinner, 2011). Despite the recent characterization of the multiple facets of traps in peripheralized regions
137 (Sarkki et al., 2025), the concept of traps still lacks a comprehensive and broadly accepted scientific definition.

138 To the best our knowledge no effort has been made to derive a scientific definition of periphery traps that
139 incorporates the aspects across multiple disciplines and scholarly perspectives.

140 2 The Proposed Approach

141 2.1 A framework for Building Consensus on Scientific Concepts

142 Phase 1: A group of domain experts is selected to contribute initial proposals for the definition.

143 Phase 2: A group of jurors is assembled to carry out content analysis, clustering and summarization of the
144 initial proposals. The group includes experts from various scientific disciplines relevant to the concept under
145 consideration, as well as generative AI chatbots. The jurors should work independently in coding, identifying
146 key terms and deciding on the number of common topics and their degree of fuzziness.

147 Phase 3: The resulting clusterings are compared both quantitatively, to evaluate their degree of similarity, and
148 qualitatively, to identify overarching thematic categories. These categories subsequently serve as evaluation
149 criteria within the multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) framework for evaluating the final definitions.

150 Phase 4: Jurors proceed with formulating their own final definitions, considering the clusters they identified
151 and the overarching themes. The AI chatbots are prompted to generate a single scientific definition, ensuring
152 that the definition incorporates as many elements of the initial proposals as possible while accounting for the
153 identified clusters.

154 Phase 5: Finally, a panel of experts evaluates the proposed definitions using the predetermined multiple criteria
155 and fuzzy MCDA.

157 **Fig. 1** Framework for formulating a consensual definition of a scientific concept

158 The details of phases 3 and 5 are described in chapters 2.2 and 2.3.

159 2.2 Phase 3: Comparison of Clusterings

160 2.2.1 Quantitative Comparison

161 In the quantitative evaluation the soft Rand index (SR_K in eq. 1) and Measure of Concordance (MoC in eq. 2,
162 Pfitzner et al., 2009) are used. SR_K is based on the Rand index (R_K), eq. 3, which counts how many of all pairs
163 of samples in the dataset (N) are either assigned to the same cluster in both partitions (a in eq. 4) or to different
164 clusters in both partitions (d in eq. 5) (Rand, 1971).

$$SR_K = \frac{\sum_{i,j} [p_{i\alpha} q_{j\beta} \delta(\alpha, \beta) + (1 - p_{i\alpha})(1 - q_{j\beta})(1 - \delta(\alpha, \beta))]}{\sum_{i,j} [p_{i\alpha} q_{j\beta} + (1 - p_{i\alpha})(1 - q_{j\beta})]} \quad (1)$$

$$MoC = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if } I = J = 1 \\ \frac{\chi^2}{N(\sqrt{IJ} - 1)}; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$R_K = \frac{a + d}{a + b + c + d} = \frac{a + d}{N} \quad (3)$$

Eq. 1 was obtained by rewriting eq. 3 using the corresponding membership probabilities $p_{i\alpha}$ and $q_{j\beta}$ to represent the probability of definition i being assigned to cluster α by juror P and definition j being assigned to cluster β by juror Q. Pairs of definitions that are assigned to the same cluster by both P and Q, i.e. a , are then calculated as:

$$a = \sum_{i,j} p_{i\alpha} q_{j\beta} \delta(\alpha, \beta), \quad (4)$$

pairs of definitions assigned to different clusters by both jurors, i.e. d , are calculated as:

$$d = \sum_{i,j} (1 - p_{i\alpha})(1 - q_{j\beta})(1 - \delta(\alpha, \beta)), \quad (5)$$

pairs of definitions assigned to the same cluster by juror P but to different clusters by juror Q, i.e. b :

$$b = \sum_{i,j} p_{i\alpha} (1 - q_{j\beta}) \delta(\alpha, \beta) \quad (6)$$

and pairs of definitions that are assigned to different clusters by P but to the same cluster by Q, i.e. c :

$$c = \sum_{i,j} (1 - p_{i\alpha}) q_{j\beta} \delta(\alpha, \beta) \quad (7)$$

The Kronecker delta function $\delta(\alpha, \beta)$ in eqs. 4 to 7 ensures that only pairs of definitions belonging to the same clusters in partitionings P and Q are considered. $\delta(\alpha, \beta)$ equals 1 if $\alpha = \beta$ and 0 otherwise.

SR_K ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating no agreement between the two jurors on any pair of definitions, and 1 indicating that the two jurors have exactly the same definitions clustered together. MoC measures the degree of concordance between two partitionings, similar to Cramer's V, but accounts for the size and number of clusters in both partitionings (I and J, respectively, Pfitzner et al., 2009). MoC ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating complete independence between P and Q, and 1 when $P = Q$. The similarity of the partitionings can be visualized by the hierarchical clustering of the jurors using the nearest neighbor method and $1 - SR_K$ as a similarity measure.

2.2.2 Qualitative Comparison

In the qualitative evaluation of the partitionings, the cluster labels and the jurors' descriptions of the clusters are analyzed for thematic similarity to identify potential overarching thematic categories (hereinafter referred

191 to as overarching themes). This process involves coding or tagging segments of text that reflect similar ideas
 192 or concepts. The overarching themes that emerge in this phase represent distinguishing characteristics (i.e.
 193 *differentiae*, Supplementary Information) that differentiate the concept from related concepts. They are then
 194 used as criteria for evaluating the final proposals in the MCDA (chapter 3.3) to select the best definition.

195 2.3 Phase 5: Multi-Criteria Evaluation of the Final Proposals

196 2.3.1 Fuzzy Numbers

197 In the multi-criteria model, experts use linguistic preferences (Table 1), which are then converted into
 198 triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs), represented by a triplet of numbers (l, m, u) , where m is the middle or the
 199 most promising value, l is the smallest possible value (lower bound), and u is the largest possible value (upper
 200 bound). Their membership function is defined by eq. 8.

$$201 \quad \mu(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-l}{m-l}, & l \leq x \leq m \\ \frac{u-x}{u-m}, & m < x \leq u \\ 0, & x < l \text{ or } x > u \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

202 The simplified fuzzy arithmetic of the basic mathematical operations of TFNs is presented in eq. 9. Let
 203 $\tilde{x}_1 = (l_1, m_1, u_1)$ and $\tilde{x}_2 = (l_2, m_2, u_2)$ be two TFNs. Then:

$$204 \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{x}_1 \oplus \tilde{x}_2 &= (l_1 + l_2, m_1 + m_2, u_1 + u_2) \\ \tilde{x}_1 \ominus \tilde{x}_2 &= (l_1 - u_2, m_1 - m_2, u_1 - l_2) \\ \tilde{x}_1 \otimes \tilde{x}_2 &= (l_1 l_2, m_1 m_2, u_1 u_2) \\ \frac{\tilde{x}_1}{\tilde{x}_2} &= \left(\frac{l_1}{u_2}, \frac{m_1}{m_2}, \frac{u_1}{l_2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

205 2.3.2 Similarity-Awarded Fuzzy Group Best -Worst Method

206 In the multi-criteria evaluation of the final proposals we use the Similarity-Awarded fuzzy group BWM
 207 (SAfBWM,) conducted in seven steps. SAfBWM retains all the advantages of BWM, while extending its
 208 capabilities by considering uncertainty and vagueness of pairwise comparisons and the desire for a final
 209 consensus decision. It allows experts to use natural language and express their preferences through linguistic
 210 scores, which are further transformed into triangular fuzzy numbers. An adapted form of fuzzy BWM linear
 211 program is then used to derive weights. Individual weights and expert importance weights are aggregated into
 212 group weights. The model assigns more importance to experts who agree on the best element in BWM,
 213 supporting consensus formation. Finally, the weights of criteria and alternatives are aggregated.

214 **Step 1:** The expert identifies the best (most important) and worst (least important) element.

215 **Step 2:** The expert rates the preference of the best element over all the other elements using a 9-point linguistic
 216 scale. The evaluations are transformed into corresponding TFNs (Table 1). The result is the best-to-others

217 vector $(\tilde{a}_{B1}, \tilde{a}_{B2}, \dots, \tilde{a}_{Bn})$, where $\tilde{a}_{Bj} = (a_{Bj}^L, a_{Bj}^M, a_{Bj}^U)$ indicates the TFN preference of the best element B over
 218 element j .

219

220 **Table 1** Transformation rules of linguistic preferences into triangular fuzzy numbers

Linguistic preferences	Corresponding triangular fuzzy number
Equally preferred	(1,1,1)
Equally to moderately preferred	(1,2,3)
Moderately preferred	(2,3,4)
Moderately to strongly preferred	(3,4,5)
Strongly preferred	(4,5,6)
Strongly to very strongly preferred	(5,6,7)
Very strongly preferred	(6,7,8)
Very strongly to extremely preferred	(7,8,9)
Extremely preferred	(9,9,9)

221

222 **Step 3:** The expert rates the preference of all elements over the worst element using a 9-point linguistic scale.
 223 The evaluations are transformed into corresponding TFNs (Table 1). The result is the others-to-worst vector
 224 $(\tilde{a}_{1W}, \tilde{a}_{2W}, \dots, \tilde{a}_{nW})$, where $\tilde{a}_{jW} = (a_{jW}^L, a_{jW}^M, a_{jW}^U)$ indicates the TFN preference of element i over the worst
 225 element W .

226 **Step 4:** Derive the weights by solving an optimization model.

227 We determine weights with the property $\frac{w_B}{w_j} \sqsubseteq \tilde{a}_{Bj}$ and $\frac{w_j}{w_W} \sqsubseteq \tilde{a}_{jW}$ for $j=1, \dots, n$, using the fuzzy linear
 228 programming model of Hafezalkotob & Hafezalkotob (2017).

229

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min \varepsilon \\
 & \text{s.t. } |w_B - \tilde{a}_{Bj} w_j| \lesssim \varepsilon \text{ for all } j, \\
 & |w_j - \tilde{a}_{jW} w_W| \lesssim \varepsilon \text{ for all } j, \\
 & \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, w_j \geq 0 \text{ for all } j,
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

231 where \lesssim denotes fuzzy less than, meaning “almost less than”. Hafezalkotob and Hafezalkotob (2017)
 232 converted fuzzy inequalities into very loose ordinary inequalities. The analysis of their model revealed the
 233 problems with measuring inconsistency. If an expert provides highly inconsistent judgments, the inconsistency
 234 measure should indicate this, and the experts should adjust their judgments. Due to the loose constraints in the
 235 linear program, the model of Hafezalkotob and Hafezalkotob (2017) does not recognize the case of highly

236 inconsistent pairwise comparisons. Therefore, we adapted the model to address its shortcomings. Let
 237 $\tilde{a}_{Bj} = (a_{Bj}^L, a_{Bj}^M, a_{Bj}^U)$. Model (10) can then be transformed into an optimization model with ordinary inequalities:

238

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min \quad \varepsilon \\
 & \text{s.t. } w_B - \varepsilon \leq \left(a_{Bj}^M + (1-\alpha)(a_{Bj}^U - a_{Bj}^M) \right) w_j \text{ for all } j, \\
 & \quad w_B + \varepsilon \geq \left(a_{Bj}^M - (1-\alpha)(a_{Bj}^M - a_{Bj}^L) \right) w_j \text{ for all } j \\
 239 & \quad w_j - \varepsilon \leq \left(a_{jW}^M + (1-\alpha)(a_{jW}^U - a_{jW}^M) \right) w_W \text{ for all } j, \quad (11) \\
 & \quad w_j + \varepsilon \geq \left(a_{jW}^M - (1-\alpha)(a_{jW}^M - a_{jW}^L) \right) w_W \text{ for all } j \\
 & \quad \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, w_j \geq 0 \text{ for all } j.
 \end{aligned}$$

240 The optimal value ε represents the consistency level of fuzzy preferences. The value of α , $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ denotes
 241 a predefined possibility level and influences the tightness of constraints. Higher values of α indicate tighter
 242 constraints and possibly result in higher inconsistency. In our model, we used $\alpha = 0.5$. We conducted a
 243 sensitivity analysis with respect to the possibility level α , which affects the tightness of the fuzzy constraints
 244 in model (11). The results demonstrated robustness across the interval $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$, as the ranking order of criteria
 245 and the associated definitions remained unchanged.

246 **Step 5:** Determine expert importance weights based on the best element using the Similarity-Awarded Group
 247 Method (Šmidovnik and Grošelj, 2023). To reinforce the pursuit of a consensual final decision, higher weights
 248 are assigned to experts who identified the same best element. We have upgraded the method so that it also
 249 works for experts who identified more than one element as the best. The weights of experts are determined
 250 separately for each hierarchy level. Let n be the number of elements and s the number of experts. Let $\#$ indicate
 251 counting and $r(w_i^{(j)})$ the rank of weight $w_i^{(j)}$ of element $i=1, \dots, n$ obtained by expert $j=1, \dots, s$. Expert j has
 252 selected one best element in BWM, but he can assign the same highest weight to more than one element. Let
 253 $I_j = \{i=1, \dots, n \mid r(w_i^{(j)})=1\}$ and let b_j denote the number of elements that received the same highest weight by
 254 expert j :

$$255 \quad b_j = \#_{k=1}^n (r(w_k^{(j)})=1) \quad (12)$$

256 Let n_i expresses the number of experts who selected element i as the best or the proportion of expert j , if they
 257 assigned the highest weight to more than one element. Let $S_i = \{j=1, \dots, s \mid r(w_i^{(j)})=1\}$. Then:

$$258 \quad n_i = \#_{j \in S_i} \left(\frac{1}{b_j} \right) \quad (13)$$

259 Then $\sum_{i=1}^n n_i = s$ and the weight of expert j is as follows:

$$\omega_j = \frac{1}{b_j} \sum_{i \in I_j} \left(\frac{n_i}{\sum_{k=1}^n n_k^2} \right). \quad (14)$$

261 The sum of all weights of experts is equal to 1.

262 **Step 6:** Aggregate individual weights into group weights by weighted arithmetic mean for criteria and
 263 alternatives regarding each criterion.

$$w_i = \sum_{j=1}^s \omega_j w_i^{(j)}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

265 **Step 7:** Aggregate group weights of criteria and alternatives by weighted arithmetic mean into final alternative
 266 group weights.

$$w_i = \sum_{j=1}^m w_{C_j} w_i^{(C_j)}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (16)$$

268 where w_{C_j} is the group weight of criterion j , $w_i^{(C_j)}$ is the group weight of alternative i regarding criterion j , m
 269 is the number of criteria and w_i is the final group weight of alternative i .

270

271 2.3.3 Distance Between Weights

272 For the comparison of individual and group weights, we chose the measure of the distance between weights
 273 (Abdelkader et al., 2024)

$$WD = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{j=1}^s \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (w_i^{(j)} - w_i)^2} \quad (17)$$

274 A lower value of WD indicates greater similarity between individual and group weights and thus a higher
 275 legitimacy of the collective preference. WD (eq. (17)) was also used to measure the consensual nature of
 276 SAFBWM by comparing the results obtained by eqs. (15) and (16) (see Table 7) with group weights derived
 277 by the arithmetic mean of individual weights, without considering the weights of experts.
 278

279

280 3 Case Study

281 3.1 Initial Proposal Collection, Content Analysis and Clustering of Proposals

282 The initial proposals for definitions were collected at the annual meeting of an international forum for
 283 knowledge synthesis, exchange and co-creation in the field of sustainability challenges in marginalized
 284 mountainous regions (MARGISTAR, <https://margistar.eu/>) in Utsjoki, Finland, in 2023. At the meeting all
 285 registered forum members ($n = 124$) were invited to describe their own understanding of a trap in marginalized

286 mountain areas. Thirty valid proposals for the definition of a trap (hereinafter a periphery trap) were received.
 287 The proposals were then thematically clustered by a social scientist (Juror A) and a natural scientist (Juror B),
 288 and two AI chatbots, ChatGPT (juror C, OpenAI, 2024) and Gemini (juror D, Google, 2024). At the time of
 289 the analysis, ChatGPT and Gemini were the latest publicly available LLMs with demonstrated applications in
 290 comparable text summarization and clustering tasks (e.g. Ficko et al., 2025; Gimpel et al., 2024; Li et al.,
 291 2024a). Juror B employed probabilistic clustering of proposals. The two chatbots were instructed to cluster the
 292 30 proposed definitions into three clusters according to their similarity using the following prompt: “Can you
 293 cluster the following 30 definitions of a periphery trap from the list below into 3 clusters according to their
 294 similarity, label the cluster, and for each cluster write the definitions that belong to the cluster in full and add
 295 the respective number from this list at the beginning of each definition.”

296 Juror A created five clusters (A1 to A5), while Juror B formed three fuzzy clusters (B1 to B3). ChatGPT and
 297 Gemini suggested their own clusters, cluster labels and descriptions (Table 2; see Supplementary Information
 298 for details).

299 **Table 2** Clusters of 30 periphery trap definitions proposed by two human jurors and two AI chatbots

Cluster	Label
Juror A (social scientist)	
A1	Status quo in political economy
A2	Polytraps
A3	Characteristics of the area
A4	Disadvantageous process
A5	Rich in resources
Juror B (natural scientist)	
B1	Static view: the state of a system, conditions, the physical place
B2	Dynamic view: the processes in the system
B3	Boundedness, circularity of the system, internal looping, insufficiency of the system to move to a better state
Juror C (ChatGPT)	
C1	Complexity of peripheries
C2	Institutional and structural factors
C3	Economic and geographical challenges
Juror D (Gemini)	
D1	Marginalization and obstacles to development
D2	Vicious cycles and unsustainable conditions
D3	Unforeseen obstacles and complex situations

300 **3.2 Similarities of the Partitionings and the Overarching Themes**

301 Overall similarity of the four partitionings was low (Fig. 2). The most similar partitionings were those by Juror
 302 A and the chatbot Gemini, with a probability of agreement equal to 0.614 (Fig. 2b). The most dissimilar

303 perspectives were those of Juror B and Gemini ($SR_k = 0.533$, Fig. 2b). Juror B's partitioning was the least
 304 similar to all other partitionings (Fig. 2a). The two human jurors agreed marginally better than the two chatbots,
 305 with SRK values of 0.566 and 0.557, respectively. The strength of association between the partitionings
 306 suggests that the four jurors interpreted the content of the proposals quite differently. Across all pairwise
 307 comparisons, the Measure of Concordance (MoC) was consistently very low (Table 3).

308

309

310 **Fig. 2** a) Similarity of the partitionings of 30 definitions by two human jurors (Jurors A and B) and two chatbots
 311 (ChatGPT and Gemini) using the nearest neighbor method and $1 - SR_k$ as a similarity measure; (b) SR_k values
 312 indicating the probability that definitions are treated alike by both jurors

313 **Table 3** Similarity measures between partitionings. Above the diagonal: Measure of Concordance (MoC¹);
 314 below the diagonal: Cramer's V

	Juror A	Juror B	ChatGPT	Gemini
Juror A		34.4	8.7	89.7
Juror B	157.3		80.3	16.4
ChatGPT	790.2	2004.4		0.68
Gemini	2537.9	906.6	185.1	

315 ¹MoC: 10^{-5}

316 From the jurors' partitionings, cluster labels and cluster descriptions, three overarching themes emerged in the
 317 qualitative content analysis: 1) physical handicaps, 2) persistent looping and 3) polytraps (Table 4, see
 318 Supplementary Information). These three overarching themes were used as content-based criteria (*differentiae*)
 319 in the evaluation of the definitions (chapter 3.5). A fourth criterion evaluated how well each definition complied
 320 with the rules for definition construction (Table 4).

321 **Table 4** Descriptions of the proposed criteria for evaluating the scientific definitions of a periphery trap

Criterion	Description of the criterion
Physical handicaps	Physical handicaps describe the limiting features of physical space in marginalized mountain areas and the multiple handicaps such as remoteness, steep slopes, lack of infrastructure, poor soils and low agricultural income.
Persistent looping	Persistent looping emphasizes the complex internal processes in marginalized mountain social-ecological systems rather than the end result of these processes.
Polytraps	Polytraps assumes that periphery traps are characterized by complex and diverse factors that render the socio-ecological system untenable.
Definition structure	This criterion evaluates how well the definition avoids circular reasoning, inconsistencies and ambiguities, and how clear, complete and precise it is.

322

323 3.3 Proposals for Common Definition

324 The jurors then formulated their final proposals (Table 5). The prompt for the two chatbots was: "Can you
 325 create one single definition of a periphery trap from the following 30 definitions provided in Table ChatGPT
 326 [name of the table uploaded]. Cluster labels are in the second column, while element of the clusters
 327 (definitions) are in lines. The definition should be scientific and include as many elements of the 30 definitions
 328 as possible while accounting for the 3 clusters. It should be in one sentence and begin with "A periphery trap
 329 is...".

330 **Table 5** Final four proposed scientific definitions of a periphery trap subject to multi-criteria evaluation

Juror	Final proposal
Juror A	A periphery trap is an undesirable socio-economic condition experienced at individual and collective levels, undermining opportunities for people in peripheral regions and difficult to solve due to reinforcement by maladaptive behavior and the influence of multiple intertwined drivers.
Juror B	A periphery trap is a complex management and decision-making situation in social-ecological systems that are physically, economically and politically disadvantaged, where the resolution is beyond the capacity of any single actor and is often controlled by external actors.
ChatGPT	A periphery trap is a set of interconnected socio-economic, environmental and institutional challenges that hinder sustainable development and conservation efforts in marginalized or remote regions by reinforcing cycles of disadvantage, limiting access to resources and technology, and perpetuating isolation and exclusion from mainstream development processes.
Gemini	A periphery trap is a self-reinforcing cycle of marginalization and unsustainable conditions in geographically isolated or disadvantaged areas, characterized by limited accessibility, socio-economic decline, environmental degradation and obstacles to development, which can be exacerbated by external policies and can hinder positive change.

332 3.4 Multi-Criteria Evaluation of the Final Proposals

333 A panel of 23 experts was selected based on their engagement in the MARGISTAR forum and their recent
 334 theoretical work on traps in marginalized mountain areas (Sarkki et al., 2025). The panelists were asked to
 335 evaluate the importance of the criteria and the four final proposals. Table 6 shows how many experts selected
 336 a given criterion or definitions as the best, using eq. (13), where the decimal values express the proportion of
 337 experts when the highest weight was assigned to more than one element. The first criterion, *Physical*
 338 *handicaps*, was selected as the most important by half of the experts (11 experts selected *Physical handicaps*
 339 as the most important, while one expert selected *Physical handicaps* and *Persistent looping* as equally
 340 important, resulting in a combined value of 11.5.). The third criterion, *Polytraps*, was the second most
 341 important, selected as most important by seven experts.

342 Most experts chose the definitions created by ChatGPT or Gemini as the best for all criteria. A similar number
 343 of experts favored one of these two definitions as the best for three of the four criteria, with the sole exception
 344 being the Polytraps criterion. The final group weights of the criteria and alternatives regarding the criteria are
 345 presented in Table 8. The final group weights of definitions are presented in Fig. 3. The results show that the
 346 definition created by ChatGPT ranked first, with a slightly higher weight than the second-placed definition by
 347 Gemini. The definitions created by Jurors B and A were placed third and fourth, respectively, and received
 348 similar but much lower weights.

349 **Table 6** The number of experts n_i (eq. 13) who assigned the highest weight to each criterion or definition

Criteria	Physical handicaps	Persistent looping	Polytraps	Definition structure
	11.5	4.5	7	0
Proposal by:				
Juror A	3	3	3	1
Juror B	2	4	3	4
ChatGPT	9	8	11.5	8
Gemini	9	8	5.5	10

350

351 **Table 7** The group weights of criteria and group weights of definitions by criterion

	Physical handicaps	Persistent looping	Polytraps	Definition structure	Final group weights of definitions
Group weights of criteria	0.426	0.194	0.262	0.118	
Proposal by					
Juror A	0.114	0.132	0.142	0.104	0.124

Juror B	0.147	0.167	0.149	0.199	0.157
ChatGPT	0.373	0.343	0.445	0.326	0.381
Gemini	0.366	0.359	0.264	0.371	0.338

352

353

354 **Fig. 3** The final group weights of scientific definitions of a periphery trap, aggregated by the weighted
 355 arithmetic mean using the Similarity-Awarded fuzzy group Best-Worst Method (SAfBWM), and the
 356 arithmetic mean

357 The final group weights derived by arithmetic mean are presented in Fig. 3, and the *WD* values are presented
 358 in Table 8. Lower *WD* values indicate higher agreement between individual and group weights. Lower *WD*
 359 values produced by SAfBWM indicate a higher degree of alignment between individual preferences and the
 360 overall group preference, compared to estimates based on the arithmetic mean.

361 **Table 8** *WD* values when comparing individual and group weights for criteria, the definitions by criterion and
 362 final scientific definitions of a periphery trap

WD	Criteria	Definitions by criterion				Scientific definitions of a periphery trap
		Physical handicaps	Persistent looping	Polytraps	Definition structure	
SAfBWM	0.234	0.249	0.268	0.222	0.220	0.184
Arithmetic mean	0.263	0.278	0.297	0.281	0.264	0.188

363 4 Discussion

364 4.1 The Use of LLMs in Consensus-Based Tasks

365 This study introduces a novel methodology for harmonizing diverse expert opinions and achieving consensus
366 in defining scientific concepts by using hybrid chatbot-expert panels and an improved MCDA. While the use
367 of LLMs for clustering and summarizing textual inputs has tremendous potential (Michel et al., 2010), the
368 applicability of open-access LLM-based chatbots in participatory decision making has not been widely
369 explored (but see Kim et al., 2021; Siemon, 2022; Yang et al., 2024). When knowledge is fragmented and
370 perspectives diverge (Lock et al., 2024; Ficko et al., 2025), or when a shared vocabulary and high consensus
371 are critical for effective decision-making (Bromme, 2000; Moilanen et al., 2021), LLM-based chatbots can
372 effectively support human decisions by bridging conceptual divides and presenting information in a coherent
373 and neutral form. Contrary to our expectations, LLM-assisted definitions were preferred over human-generated
374 ones by a factor of 2.6 to 1 (Fig. 3). This result is consistent with findings from several studies in which users
375 overwhelmingly preferred ChatGPT summaries over those written by humans (Goyal et al., 2022; Zhang and
376 Gosline, 2023).

377 The significant difference likely stems from several factors. First, ChatGPT and Gemini can produce highly
378 organized and precise definitions that align closely with established scientific writing styles. In contrast, the
379 two human jurors employed more varied approaches, possibly due to their different scientific backgrounds,
380 characterizing periphery traps as “socioeconomic conditions” (Juror A) and “management and decision-
381 making situation” (Juror B), both of which are relatively vague characterizations. The chatbots, by contrast,
382 used more concrete language, referring to traps as “a set of interconnected socio-economic, environmental,
383 and institutional challenges” (ChatGPT) and “a self-reinforcing cycle” (Gemini). Second, LLMs can access
384 extensive databases of terminology, which likely contributed to more precisely worded definitions. Third,
385 cognitive and subjective differences between human experts should not be underestimated in the panels. The
386 two human jurors likely prioritized contrasting aspects of the definition based on their personal experience,
387 which might not have been recognized by the wider panel. As a result, the more general and inclusive AI-
388 generated outputs may have received broader support. That said, the results do not suggest that AI-generated
389 definitions are inherently superior. A hybrid approach—integrating key human knowledge into machine
390 learning rather than merely using chatbots as panelists with limited authority and autonomy—may enhance
391 chatbot performance and promote more autonomous use of LLMs in expert decision making (e.g. Xu et al.,
392 2023; Long et al., 2024;). Despite the potential of LLMs, the similarity between the two machine-generated
393 clusterings was surprisingly low. This result suggests that open-access chatbots should be used with caution
394 and only after verifying whether a model produces consistent responses to queries that are semantically
395 equivalent but phrased differently. We tested the internal consistency of ChatGPT’s and Gemini’s responses
396 by repeating the same prompts in a new chat after a time delay and comparing the responses (Zhang and
397 Gosline, 2023). While the answers were structurally similar and argued in comparable ways, they varied in

398 specific details, confirming earlier findings that LLMs continue to suffer from low factual consistency (Liang
399 et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2024). To address these challenges, we propose 1) iterative consensus-building to
400 establish a minimum shared vocabulary (phase 3) and 2) integrating AI into decision-making through an
401 “augmented human” approach, rather than through “AI-only” or “augmented AI” models (Zhang and Gosline,
402 2023). In the “augmented human” approach, “a human expert makes the final decision on the output but is
403 given the content first generated by ChatGPT-4 for the task, which they may edit or use as an inspiration.” A
404 similar conclusion was reached by Flamino, et al. (2025) in their study on the potential use of LLM-powered
405 agents as artificial partners, suggesting that such agents must evolve further before they can function
406 effectively as surrogates or confederates to humans.

407 **4.2 Enhanced Consistency Evaluation in the Fuzzy Best-Worst Method**

408 The improved weight derivation in the fuzzy BWM ensures that the inconsistency score more accurately
409 reflects inconsistencies in individual pairwise comparisons. Inconsistency in fuzzy multi-criteria evaluation is
410 generally more problematic than in crisp methods because in fuzzy MCDM, expert opinions are expressed
411 with linguistic terms, which introduces subjectivity and uncertainty in the interpretation of the linguistic scale.
412 Moreover, since these scales involve overlapping membership functions, small inconsistencies can compound,
413 making it more difficult to maintain a coherent weight distribution. While crisp MCDM methods have well-
414 defined consistency indices (e.g. Saaty’s Consistency Ratio in AHP), defining and quantifying inconsistency
415 in fuzzy methods remains more challenging, and no universally accepted approach has emerged. Our method
416 for determining weights, based on the improved optimization model by Hafezalkotob and Hafezalkotob
417 (2017), allows for the selection of a predefined possibility level (α), which influences the tightness of
418 constraints. Higher values of α impose tighter constraints and result in greater consistency. The analyst can
419 adjust α according to the desired constraint tightness. Our preliminary sensitivity analysis with varying α
420 suggests a small but non-negligible effect of constraint tightness on weight derivation. Further analysis is
421 needed to decompose the total inconsistency score into components attributable to the selected membership
422 function, constraint tightness and true inconsistency in the decision maker’s judgments.

423 **4.3 Similarity-Awarded Aggregation in Group Decision-Making**

424 Consensus-building remains a critical challenge in multi-expert decision-making. To address this, we
425 integrated the similarity-awarded group method developed by Šmidovnik and Grošelj (2023), which accounts
426 for agreement among experts’ judgments. Unlike standard aggregation methods, which treat all expert opinions
427 equally, this approach rewards consensual behavior by assigning higher weights to alternatives receiving
428 similar evaluations from multiple experts. As demonstrated by Guo and Qi (2021), such methods foster
429 agreement and reduce the impact of extreme or inconsistent judgments. Other criteria such as trust relationships
430 and trust scores may be used for determining the weights of decision-makers (Diao et al., 2025). The SAfBWM
431 ensures that alternatives widely recognized as the best by multiple experts receive proportionally greater
432 weight, leading to a more robust and widely accepted group decision. The lower values of WD obtained in our

433 study confirm that SAfBWM achieved higher similarity between individual and group weights than the
434 arithmetic mean, indicating a higher degree of consensus. Importantly, SAfBWM does not promote groupthink
435 or the marginalization of non-mainstream but valuable opinions, as it preserves the independence of individual
436 decision-makers; rather than suppressing diversity to artificially boost consensus, it enhances the legitimacy
437 of the collective preference by organically assigning more weight to more consensual decision makers.

438 **4.4 Refined Weight Derivation for Equal-ranked Alternatives**

439 A further methodological innovation in our study is the refined weight derivation process, which addresses
440 cases where two alternatives are evaluated as equally good, and one of them is also rated as best, resulting in
441 tied ranks. The original similarity-awarded group method (Šmidovnik and Grošelj, 2023) did not account for
442 such scenarios, nor did it appropriately adjust the weights for tied ranks. Our novel approach ensures that when
443 multiple alternatives receive the highest evaluation, their weights are adjusted accordingly, maintaining a fair
444 representation of expert consensus. This refinement is crucial in situations where the decision-making process
445 involves nuanced or closely comparable options, as was the case in defining periphery traps. In our study, tied
446 evaluations occurred in six cases across both criteria and alternatives.

447 **4.5 Implications and Future Research**

448 The integration of AI-assisted aggregation and novel fuzzy decision-making methods offers a replicable
449 framework for consensus-building in various scientific domains. Constructing concepts is particularly pivotal
450 in social and transdisciplinary research. Beyond terminology management, the presented approach can be
451 applied to other domains where high consensus and consistency of ratings are crucial and where more
452 sophisticated LLM applications, such as Multi-expert Prompting (Xu et al., 2023; Long et al., 2024) and other
453 methods to incorporate the experts' judgment into the machine learning models (Deng et al., 2020; Park et al.,
454 2023), are not yet implemented or lack the trust of human experts. Future research should further investigate
455 consistency estimation methods in fuzzy BWM and assess the consistency of AI-generated decisions in hybrid
456 chatbot-expert consensual decision processes. Another important task in consensus processes is to provide
457 insights into how the decisions were reached—through clear explanation and visualization of the consensus-
458 building process (Felfernig et al., 2018). Since consensus indicates the ability of group members to resolve
459 conflicting views, explanations and visualizations of the commonalities and divergences may show where the
460 conflicts still persist (Tran et al., 2024).

461 **5 Conclusion**

462 This study presents several methodological and empirical advancements in the use of LLM-based chatbots in
463 mixed AI-expert decision-making processes. First, we demonstrated that open-access LLMs such as ChatGPT
464 can effectively support expert panels by analyzing and generating structured and precise scientific definitions,
465 which are preferred over those created by human jurors. However, the inconsistencies observed between the
466 LLMs underscore the need for careful validation before relying on them as autonomous panelists. Second, we

467 enhanced the logical consistency evaluation in the fuzzy BWM by integrating an improved weight derivation
468 mechanism that reflects inconsistencies more accurately, particularly under varying constraint tightness levels.
469 Third, in the group BWM setting, we applied a Similarity-Awarded aggregation technique that rewards expert
470 agreement, leading to more widely supported group decisions. Fourth, we introduced a refined weight
471 derivation method for handling tied ranks among alternatives, ensuring correct representation in cases of equal
472 preference.

473

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